

WEAVE/OneDanceUK

Fundraising 101: Operating as a Global Majority Fundraiser in 2022

Produced in collaboration with OneDanceUK, this capacity-building event/webinar aimed at supporting UK-based Global Majority dance artists to better understand the current UK fundraising landscape and to discover how to navigate their own narrative of being a Global Majority practitioner when creating a case for support. The event enabled participants to gain an overview from the Arts Council England (ACE) on Project Grant pathways (guest speaker: Will Southworth) and hear from the Chartered Institute of Fundraising (CiOF) about their RAISE programme (guest speaker: David Mbaziira). Guest speakers also included inclusive fundraising expert and co-founder of The Women of Colour Global Network, Haseena Farid. The event aimed to support participants to build confidence and knowledge and, most importantly, join the conversation on how to weave the vital experiences, identities, and expertise of Global Majority communities into potentially successful funding bids. The event was live BSL translated and close-captioned.

Key takeaways:

- There's still a long way to go before we see true equity in the arts and cultural sector.
- Funders need global majority organisations who are already reaching these communities.
- An opportunity exists to get this work higher up the agenda.
- Use your individual power to get your fundraising into "pole position" to be ready for the opportunities when they arise.
- Consider the opportunities to connect with your peers and the power of the collective in your ask
- Be strategic with your time - carefully plan and map which funders to go for
- The power of the collective – learn and understand from one another, use our networks, what to do when you make an ask and you want to follow through, how to strengthen that relationship

How to successfully engage a case for support?

- Be able to explain clearly what it is that you do and impact of your work right now and in the future; why is your work relevant.
- The need to have a confidence in own ability and a tenacity to pick yourself up, dust yourself off and go again – never give up.
- Create an 'Elevator pitch' – can you convey in 90 secs what you do and why should funders support it; hook in, then talk about progression – clearly convey essence of what we do and what their support would mean (for audience and impact).